

Integrative design: Applying Vaastu Shastra to washroom for enhanced productivity and well-being

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Abstract

Vaastu Shastra, an ancient Indian architectural science, prescribes principles for designing spaces that harmonize with natural elements and promote well-being. Applying Vaastu Shastra principles to the design of washrooms involves aligning spatial orientation, materials, and layout to optimize energy flow and create a balanced environment. This abstract explores the integration of Vaastu Shastra in washroom design, highlighting its influence on aspects such as placement of fixtures, ventilation, and use of colors to enhance hygiene, comfort, and psychological well-being. By aligning modern architectural practices with Vaastu Shastra guidelines, washroom designs can potentially contribute to a more harmonious and auspicious living environment.

Keywords: Vaastu Shastra, ancient architecture, energy flow, spatial orientation, harmonious design, natural elements, balanced environment, fixture placement, ventilation, color psychology

Introduction

Vastu Shastra is an ancient Indian science of architecture that aims to harmonize living spaces with natural forces to enhance well-being and prosperity. In the context of washrooms, Vastu emphasizes proper placement, orientation, and design to maintain the flow of positive energy and minimize negativity.

Background

Vastu Shastra is an ancient Indian architectural science designed to align living spaces with natural forces for enhanced well-being. Originating over 5,000 years ago, it aims to harmonize the five elements-earth, water, fire, air, and space.

Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the applicability of Vaastu principles in modern office design and assess their impact on employee productivity and well-being. Specific goals include:

Promote Positive Energy

- 1 Maintain Hygiene
- 2 Optimize Space
- 3 Ensure Proper Drainage
- 4 Enhance Comfort
- 5 Prevent Negative Energy
- 6 Support Overall Harmony
- 7 Utilize Natural Light
- 8 Balance Elements
- 9 Boost Well-Being

Methodology

- **Location:** Place the washroom in the northwest or west of the house, avoiding the northeast corner.
- **Doors:** Ensure the door opens inward and faces north or east.
- **Toilets and Showers:** Position the commode so users face north or south.
- **Colours:** Use light, soothing colors for walls.
- **Ventilation:** Ensure good airflow with windows or exhaust fans.

- **Storage:** Avoid keeping health-related items inside.
- **Cleanliness:** Maintain cleanliness regularly.

Literature Review

Principles of Vaastu Shastra

Vaastu Shastra is rooted in five fundamental elements: earth, water, fire, air, and space. Each element corresponds to specific directions and has unique effects on human health and behavior. Key principles include:

- Orientation and layout of the building.
- Placement of furniture and workstations.
- Use of natural light and ventilation.
- Incorporation of natural elements.

Vaastu for bathroom and toilet - Toilet direction as per Vaastu

Bathrooms and toilets Vaastu are separated places, and they differ from each other. Toilets Vaastu refer to the site where the commode and washbasin are the essential parts. We usually use this portion for relieving ourselves. But we use bathrooms for refreshing and changing ourselves apart from just relieving. But usually, in most of the house, the word 'bathroom' means both bathroom and toilet together in one word. So, Vaastu for bathroom refers to this combination of both. However, at our grandparents' age, they usually made a toilet outside of the house. But in the world of 7 billion people, where the living place is limited, we have no way but to plan attached bathrooms and toilets.

Designing and remodeling their living space are the chief concerns of most families. But Vaastu for toilets and bathrooms are neglected. Do you know? It is the most frequently used place in every house than any other room of the house. Then how could we leave Vaastu for toilet uncared? To make a Vaastu-compliant home, you also have to take care of Vaastu for bathrooms and toilets as per toilet Vaastu principles. An incorrectly placed bathroom/toilet as per Vaastu shastra space generates lots of negative energy. You are facing the loss of wealth, health hazards, even minor accidents. But you don't find any reason behind it. Your non-Vaastu-compliant toilet or bathrooms may be responsible for this.

Content of article

Do you live in your ancestor's house, and is it not possible for you to construct a new bathroom cum toilet as per Vaastu on your home property? Don't panic! Here we come with our most discussed topics and Vaastu tips to construct or remodel a bathroom or rectify the Vaastu defects for toilets and bathrooms.

- Toilet direction as per Vaastu
- Vaastu guidelines for the toilet seat
- Vaastu colours for toilet
- The flooring of the toilet
- Installation of water facilities
- Installation of equipment in the bathroom
- Vaastu for toilet water drainage
- Few Vaastu tips to enhance bathroom and toilet

interiors

- General Vaastu tips for designing Vaastu perfect toilet or bathroom

Toilet direction as per Vaastu

Placement of the bathroom or toilet as per Vaastu is one of the most important things we should keep in mind whenever we build a new toilet in our housing plot or buy a house or flat. As previously said, incorrect placement may lead our lives in great danger. Here we come with the best and worst placement of toilet as per Vaastu.

Best placement directions of lavatory according to 'Vaastu Shastra.'

East of northeast or East (Only for Bathrooms, not Toilets)

This direction, as per Vaastu for the bathroom, is the best choice for the bathing area. The energies of this zone make you feel more energetic after bathing, as it activates the internal positive vast energies inside us. But this east or east of northeast zone is only for making your favourite bathing area. According to Applied Vaastu experts, placing a commode in this zone is strictly prohibited.

East of southeast (ESE)

This zone is also an extremely favourable zone for placing the toilet as well as a bathroom. A toilet in this zone has many mentionable benefits. It keeps anxiety, panic, and stress-related problems at bay. But suppose you are involved with any analytical jobs (i.e., economist, accountant or technical writer, engineer, scientist, etc.). In that case, a toilet in this direction is not a good idea for you as per bathroom Vaastu.

South of the southwest (SSW)

This zone is again the best place for making a toilet as per Vaastu. This zone is referred to as the zone of disposal according to 'Vaastu Shastra.' So, suppose you want to get rid of all wasteful stuff from your life and not only human waste but also emotional waste or mental waste or useless relationships as per the Vaastu rules of the toilet. In that case, this zone is ideal for constructing the bathroom or lavatory as per Vaastu.

West of the northwest (WNW)

According to 'Vaastu Shastra,' this zone is also called the zone of 'Rodan Graha' (a place where we release all our blocked emotions by crying). So, placing a toilet as per Vaastu in this zone helps the residents of your house release and remove long blocked emotions from their minds and hearts. We all know releasing negative emotions also allows us to free from any disease. In general, It is the best direction for the placement of toilets and bathrooms as per Vaastu shastra. Again, toilets in this direction are not a good idea for the persons involved with esoteric or cult practices, as per principles Vaastu of toilets.

Fig 1: Toilet position as per Vastu shastra

The worst placement directions of lavatory according to 'Vaastu Shastra.'

There are specific zones or directions considered the worst for placement of our bathrooms or toilet Vaastu. We should better avoid these directions if it is not inevitable.

East

Suppose you have already made your toilet in this zone. You should think again about reconstructing it if it is not inevitable because the toilet in this zone affects your life greatly. You face health hazards related to the liver and gallbladder-lavatory in east direction causes social issue. Even if you do not find a suitable life partner for you if you have a toilet in this zone. On the other hand, bathrooms in the east direction are preferable as per Vaastu shastra. It would help if you remembered the east bathroom is only used for bathing purposes.

West

What is the use of the Vaastu for the toilet? As we know, the toilet Vaastu is used as a disposal area for our body waste. So, if you are a business person looking for profits, business expansion, you face trouble with the toilet in the west direction. So, better avoid making toilets Vaastu in this west direction of your home.

South

Making a toilet as per Vaastu in the southern part of your home or flat will be another wrong decision, as a toilet in the south attracts legal troubles and court cases and causes health problems. So, according to Vaastu shastra, do not make your toilet in the south zone.

North

This direction is for Lord Kuber-the giver of wealth, which

is considered as the most promising direction. A toilet in the north direction creates hurdles in every opportunity to earn money or in your career, according to Vaastu experts.

Northeast

Bathrooms or toilets in the northeast direction have many adverse effects, such as serious health problems (neurological problems), financial crisis, and blockage of the flow of ideas according to bathroom Vaastu. So, if you don't want to invite many issues in your life, 'Vaastu Shastra' advises you not to build a lavatory in the northeast direction.

Southeast

Are you expecting childbirth in your family? A bathroom or toilet in this direction may cause serious health risks for the unborn child. Placement of toilets in the southeast order causes serious health issues mainly to the female residents of your house. As per Vaastu rules, business people in the family should also avoid toilets in the southeast if they do not want their payment delayed or blocked.

Northwest

Like other worst directions, the northwest zone also has many unpleasant side effects on our lives. This zone is known for disturbing the foundation of anything in life. Do you face property disputes like delays in building a building, or don't you get proper support from the right people when you need it? According to 'Vaastu Shastra, the bathroom in the northwest may be responsible for all your problems.'

South West

Construction of toilets in the southwest is the wrong decision, as the southwest direction is strictly prohibited for building lavatory as per Vaastu. A bathroom in the southwest direction may cause physical, mental, financial instability in life. It also affects relationships with each other in your family as Moola Dhara Chakra (responsible for stability in life) within the body, which the southwest direction represents, is significantly affected by the bathroom or toilet in the southwest direction.

Toilet seat direction as per Vaastu / Vaastu for Toilet seat Facing

There are two types of toilet seats–The Indian and the western toilet system. We can choose any toilet seat or both according to Vaastu shastra. In the present world, most people live in apartments and flats. So, it is practically impossible always to follow the toilet seat facing directions. But if it is not inevitable, we should avoid facing the toilet seat as per Vaastu.

East facing toilet seat as per Vaastu

This direction is wrong for the toilet seat facing as per Vaastu. This is the direction where Surya Bhagawan rises every morning. So, we insult him if we show our back to him as we treat him as God. This action leads to significant health problems in a family, according to 'Vaastu Shastra.'

West facing toilet seat as per Vaastu shastra

This is another wrong direction for toilet seat facing, strictly prohibited according to the Vaastu guidelines for the toilet seat. It causes serious health problems, especially migraine-related problems.

Northeast facing toilet seat

According to the Vaastu guidelines for the toilet seat, the northeast direction is another wrong direction for the toilet seat, disturbing your entire home positive fields. However, specific directions like south, north, south or southwest, west-northwest, east of southeast are favourable zones for toilet seat facing as per Vaastu guidelines for the toilet. Closing the toilet seat lid after use and proper cleaning of the bathroom ensure better Vaastu with hygiene. So, do you decide to install a western commode in your toilet? Wait! Before installing, better get a Vaastu Shastra consultant recommendation.

Vaastu colours for bathrooms and toilets

We know it is indeed difficult to choose among so many beautiful shades for your bathroom Vaastu. But as per the Vaastu for the toilet, not all beautiful shades are suitable for your bathroom. It would help if you opted for white, light shades of brown, pink, yellow for your bathroom. Avoid black, dark shades of red, or even blue for bathroom walls, attracting negative energy. Colour of the toilet as per Vaastu be chosen as per its location.

The flooring of the toilet Vaastu

According to Vaastu for bathroom and toilet, we should use marble or tile flooring for the bathroom. The sloping should be towards the east or north to ensure the water drains from the same sides (i.e., east or north). It is believed that this water contains toxins, negative energies, and evil thoughts. So, draining the water in the east or north direction is good for health. Many people choose dark tiles for the toilet. But you cannot spot dirt and clean your toilet areas for it. The untidy place is not only unhygienic but is the source of negative energies. For this reason, the Vaastu consultants never recommend dark tiles for flooring.

Installation of water facilities

The installation of water facilities plays a crucial role in a proper Vaastu-compliant bathroom. North, east, and

Fig 2: Placement of toilet as per Vastu Shastra

northeast zones of the bathroom are highly recommended for washbasin and shower. The same should be applied if you have a bathtub in your bathroom.

Installation of equipment in the bathroom

Could anyone imagine modern bathrooms without electronic gadgets? Modern equipment (like geysers, hairdryers, etc.) make our bathing experience more comfortable in present days. But according to the Vaastu experts, we should also follow Vaastu guidelines in installing equipment in the bathroom. Electrical equipment like geysers and hairdryers must be placed on the southeast side of the toilet.

Vaastu for water toilet drainage

An exemplary water drainage system is also necessary per Vaastu of toilet and bathroom if you want to bring positive energy to your home. The outlet of water and drainage in the bathroom and toilet, according to Vaastu, should be north, east or northeast. You always have to ensure that the water gets adequately drained. Water blockage in the bathroom generates negative energy. So, to make sure, slope the flooring of your toilet slightly. It would help if you also made sure that the pipes of the toilets and bathrooms should be redirected to the west or the northwest.

Fig 3: Interior placement for toilet

Few Vaastu tips to enhance bathroom interiors

We have to pay attention to specific facts of bathroom interiors to enhance the Vastu for the bathroom:

1. We should choose the colours according to the zones of the bathroom.
2. South of southwest-Cream
3. West of the northwest- Grey, white, cream, or blue.
4. East of the southeast- Cream, or green colour.
5. You should better install tiles to save the bathroom walls from getting damp.
6. Always keep your toilet area well-lit and refreshed. It attracts positive energies.

General Vaastu tips for designing Vaastu perfect bathroom

After a brief description of bathroom Vaastu and a few tips to enhance bathroom interiors, here we come with some Vaastu tips for toilet about what to do and what to avoid to make our bathrooms Vaastu perfect.

What to do

1. It would help if you always constructed your toilet 1-2 feet higher than ground level.
2. According to toilet Vaastu specialists, you should better fix the commode on a slightly higher platform than the rest of the floor level of your bathroom.
3. The entrance door of the toilet should be on the east or north wall.
4. The toilet window should be on the east or northwest wall.
5. We must not forget to place the mirrors in the bathroom on the northern or the eastern wall.
6. The toilet door should be made of wood instead of metal as per bathroom Vaastu. A metal door causes negativity and adverse health effects.
7. According to the Vaastu principles of the bathroom, to balance the energy field in your home, keep the bathroom door closed all the time. This action prevents hurdles in both your relationships and career.
8. As per Vaastu, for the bathroom, take a bath on the north or east side of the toilet. The north-western corner is ideal for keeping the clothes that need to be washed.

What we to avoid

1. As per toilet Vaastu rules, you should not have a water closet above or under the pooja room, fire, or bedroom.
2. The centre of the house is known as Brahmas than. It would help if you strictly avoided this area for planning any toilet or bathroom.
3. It would help if you did not place the toilet next to the puja room. They should not share the same wall, according to ‘Vaastu Shastra.’
4. Never use decorative statues, symbols, or any religious idols embellished on the door to your bathroom.
5. Your bathrooms never should face the bed as per bathroom Vaastu.

FAQ.

Q 1. Can a toilet and kitchen have a common wall, and can they be placed next to each other?

Answer: The answer is yes, in a specific direction they can. However, it is a common belief that the kitchen and toilet can never share a common wall. But as previously said, the east or southeast direction is suitable for the toilet area, and we know the southeast, the zone next to the east of southeast, is considered among the best locations for the kitchen. So, we can see, there is no problem for a kitchen and toilet to share the same wall. Toilet and kitchen can be placed next to each other in the correct zone as per our observation.

Q 2. Can a toilet seat be placed under a staircase?

Answer: Though there are mixed theories about it. But according to Applied Vaastu experts, the correct zone only matters in this case. If your toilet is placed in the right location, like the west of northwest or the south or

southwest or east of southeast, then there is no problem. The toilet can easily be placed under a staircase.

Q 3. Which direction should a person face while sitting on a toilet seat?

Answer: According to the toilet Vaastu rules, the south or north direction is ideal for a person while sitting in the toilet.

Q 4. Should the toilet be separate from the bathroom?

Answer: If it is not inevitable, you have enough space for it; you can make them separately to ensure good Vaastu.

Q 5. What are the Vaastu rules for the bathroom with the attached toilet?

Answer: Here we come with a few rules for the bathroom with an attached toilet according to 'Vaastu Shastra,' mentioned below: We should not fix the commode above or under a puja room or even a fire or bed space. The commode must be aligned on the north-south axis. 'Installation of the toilet in the centre of the house, northeast or southwest corner of your home is a strict no. The septic tank elevation must be higher than the floor level of the building and should be towards the west direction of the house or the northwest of the house. We should never make an attached toilet on the southeast or southwest side. The southwest or southeast is not ideal for placing taps and water storage. You must avoid this.

Q 6. What is the right place for placing a septic tank, as per Vaastu?

Answer: The west of northwest (WNW) part is the best direction for installing a septic tank, according to 'Vaastu Shastra.' For west facing house septic tank can be built in the south of the southwest zone.

Q 7. Can we build a toilet in the southeast corner?

Answer: No, we should always keep the southeast corner free of defects if we want a steady, progressive and peaceful life. So, we should not build a toilet in the southeast corner of our house according to toilet Vaastu.

Q 8. Can the toilet be North?

Answer: No, Lord Kuber is the governor of the north direction -the giver of wealth. So, North is considered as the most auspicious direction for carrier, wealth, and opportunity. A toilet in this direction may create hurdles in every opportunity to earn money or in your career.

Q 9. Is the south direction good for the toilet?

Answer: No, this direction is considered the worst director of the toilet, according to Vaastu shastra. Building a toilet in the south direction harms the social reputation of the people in your house.

Q 10. Can we construct a toilet in the northwest corner?

Answer: No, constructing a toilet in this corner is not advisable, according to Vaastu shastra. It may cause delays in building construction and may face bank-related issues. The bathroom in this zone may be responsible for all your problems.

Q 11. Which side is best for the toilet?

Answer: Toilet is the place of the activity of disposal and detoxification. So, if you want to get rid of all wasteful stuff from your life, as per Vaastu, construct a toilet in the south of southwest or west of northwest zone, this side being the zone of disposals best side for the toilet.

Conclusion

Do you know many of us save that extra money for other rooms that may go in decorating the toilet? Stop this action immediately! Because as previously said, Vaastu for toilet and bathroom plays a crucial role in making your house Vaastu-compliant and saves your family from adverse negative effects. So, while moving to a new house or renovating your existing residence, or to know more about bathroom Vaastu.

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